

Fertilizers, 180-60-30 kg NPK/ha, were applied, phosphorus and potash as basal and N in three splits: 1/3 basal, 1/3 at tillering, 1/3 at panicle initiation. Plant spacing was 15 × 15 cm.

EC/ WP fungicides were sprayed at tillering, panicle initiation, and flowering. Granular fungicides were applied 30 kg/ha when initial Bl symptoms appeared during tillering and 40 kg/ha during flowering. Leaf and neck Bl were measured 10 d after last application from five 1-m² random samples.

All the EC/WP fungicides but Natural Plant Product-1 effectively reduced leaf Bl (see table). Neck Bl was not reduced.

Granular fungicides chlobenthiazole 5 G and pyroquilon 5 G effectively controlled leaf Bl. Neck Bl incidence was not reflected in yield. Plots that showed

Influence of new EC/WP and granular fungicides on incidence of Bl and yield of IR50. Nellore, India. 1985-86.

Fungicide	Concentration	Leaf Bl (%)	Neck Bl (%)	Grain yield (kg/plot)
<i>EC/WP fungicides</i>				
Carbendazim 50 WP	1 g/liter	2.2	24.3	1.6
Edifenphos 50 EC	1 ml/liter	1.9	16.4	2.2
Pyroquilon 50 WP	1 g/liter	1.7	26.3	1.9
Isoprothiolane 40 EC	1 ml/liter	1.4	17.1	1.8
IBP 48 EC	1 ml/liter	2.0	20.1	1.7
Natural Plant Product – 1	2.5 ml/liter	36.3	26.5	0.9
Thiophanate methyl 70 WP	1 g/liter	2.2	23.3	1.3
Untreated check		32.9	30.8	0.8
LSD (0.05)		18.6	ns	0.6
<i>Granular fungicides</i>				
Chlobenthiazole 6 G	70 kg/ha	2.0	32.2	2.4
Pyroquilon 5 G	70 kg/ha	0.7	20.4	3.0
IBP 17 G	70 kglha	39.4	17.2	1.5
Probenazole 8 G	70 kg/ha	46.7	21.6	0.9
Untreated check		81.5	10.3	0.5
LSD (0.05)		33.1	11.4	1.0

more leaf Bl infection had few panicles with neck Bl, perhaps because panicles

on severely leaf Bl-affected plants only partially emerged. □

Insect management

Effect of lunar phase on attraction of rice pests to black light trap

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We collected rice insect pests in a Krishi Prakash Black Light Trap (KPBL-T) during six lunar cycles.

Three days on either side of the date of a full moon was taken as a full moon

week. Three days on either side of a new moon was taken as a new moon week. In-between periods formed the last and first quarter moon week. From total insect catches, ratios were obtained to compare full moon week catches with new moon week catches.

Moonlight had a significant effect on nocturnal activity of stem borer (SB), leafhopper (LF), brown planthopper (BPH), and green leafhopper (GLH). Full moon and new moon week ratios were 1:1.1, 1:1.2, 1:2.2, and 1:2.3, respectively (see table). This indicates that nocturnal activity of SB and LF is much less influenced by moonlight than that of BPH and GLH. □

Severe outbreak of rice gall midge (GM) in the savannah zone, Nigeria

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The savannah zone of Nigeria, stretching latitudinally across the southern midsection, with its river floodplains and inland valley swamps, is an important rice-growing area. Production probably accounts for more than 70% of Nigeria's total. Varieties grown include FARO 12 (Mas), FARO 13 (IR8), FARO 15, FARO 16, FARO 18 (Tjina or China), FARO 26 (TOs 78), FARO 29 (BG90-2), and IR5.

A severe outbreak of GM (*Orseolia oryzivora* H & G.) damaged crops sown Jul-Aug 1988 (wet season). Earlier (Jun-Jul) crops had little damage.

The Abakaliki locality in Anambra State (8° 10' E, 6° 20' N) had the most severe damage. Incidence of silvershoots was high (45-80% of all tillers). Yields in

Effect of lunar cycle on the black light trap catches of some rice pests. Madurai, India.

Insect	Insects ^a (no.)				Ratio of full moon week to new moon week
	Full moon week	Last quarter week	New moon week	First quarter week	
Yellow SB <i>Scirpophaga incertulas</i>	291.04 (1.94)	264.81 (1.89)	332.95 (2.30)	194.69 (1.98)	1:1.1
LF <i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	169.73 (1.55)	176.88 (1.90)	202.25 (2.19)	63.76 (1.50)	1:1.2
BPH <i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	159.80 (2.00)	157.14 (2.09)	376.11 (2.47)	128.45 (1.92)	1:2.4
GLH <i>Nephotettix</i> spp.	193.53 (1.82)	146.86 (2.10)	455.43 (2.64)	175.58 (2.09)	1:2.3

^a Mean of six lunar cycles. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.